

Condition of Iodic, Hydrofluoric and Chromic Acids and their Salts in Aqueous Solution.

BY N. R. DHAR.

In this communication I shall show that iodic and hydrofluoric acids and their salts exist mainly as $\text{H}_2\text{I}_2\text{O}_6$ and $\text{M}_2\text{I}_2\text{O}_6$, and H_2F_2 and M_2F_2 . The ions given out from iodic acid and its salts are in the bivalent condition and are to be represented as $\text{I}_2\text{O}_6''$ and those given out from fluorides exist as F_2'' .

I have also discussed the condition of chromic acid in aqueous solution and determined the second dissociation constant of this acid from solubility experiments.

Iodic Acid and Iodates.

In 1874 J. Thomsen came to the conclusion from various arguments that unlike chloric and bromic acids, iodic acid is dibasic and should be represented by $\text{H}_2\text{I}_2\text{O}_6$. Rosenheim and Liebknecht (*Liebig's Annalen*, 1899, **308**, 40) and Groschuff (*Ziet. anorg. Chem.*, 1906, **47**, 33) determined the molecular conductivity and the freezing point lowering and the elevation of the boiling points of solutions of iodic acid and the following values of i (Van't Hoff's coefficient) were obtained :—

v	1	2	3	4	5·3	16
i (electric conductivity)	1·43	1·53	—	1·63	—	1·81
i (cryoscopic)	0·95	1·21	—	1·41	—	1·67
i (ebullioscopic)	—		1·16	—	1·21	—

Hence it appears that iodic acid has a tendency to exist in the polymerised state. This conclusion is also supported from the following equivalent conductivity results of chloric and iodic acids.

V	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024
Chloric acid...	353	364	373	381	387	391	399	402	402	402
Iodic acid ...	192	230	268	301	328	350	364	372	377	380

The conclusion regarding the condition of iodic acid in aqueous solution from the above physico-chemical results has been corroborated from coagulation experiments performed with positively charged ferric hydroxide solution and iodic acid and iodates. Giolitti (*Gazzetta*, 1905, 35, II, 181 ; 1906, 36, II, 157, 433) observed that considerable amounts of HCl, HBr, HI, HNO₃, HClO₄, and HBrO₃ must be added to ferric hydroxide solution in order to effect precipitation. The hydroxide came down as a brick red powder which was peptised by water when the acid was washed out. He found further that traces of sulphurous, selenious, iodic, periodic and phosphoric acids and salts effected precipitation. Under these conditions he observed that the precipitate was gelatinous and did not redissolve on washing.

Weiser and Middleton (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1920, 24, 30) working with a solution of ferric hydroxide containing 1.54 grs. Fe₂O₃ per litre obtained the following precipitation values of potassium salts:—

		Amount required.	Precipitation value in milliequivalents.
Ferrocyanide	...	1.05 c. c. N/100	0.275
Ferricyanide	...	1.10 ,, ,,	0.287
Sulphate	...	1.70 ,, ,,	0.437
Oxalate	...	1.85 ,, ,,	0.475
Chromate	...	2.55 ,, ,,	0.650
Iodate	...	3.55 ,, ,,	0.900
Bromate	...	2.40 " N/2	31.3
Thiocyanate	...	3.65 ,, ,,	46.9
Chloride	...	8.00 ,, ,,	103.1
Chlorate	...	9.00 ,, ,,	111.6
Nitrate	...	10.25 ,, ,,	131.2

With acids the following results were obtained by Weiser and Middleton:

Acid.	Electrolyte.	Precipitation values in milliequivalents.
Dichromic	0.75 c. c. N/100	0.200
Tartaric	1.85 ,, ,,	0.475
Sulphuric	1.90 ,, ,,	0.485
Citric	1.90 ,, ,,	0.500
Oxalic	2.05 ,, ,,	0.525
Iodic	2.35 ,, ,,	0.600
Phosphoric	3.40 ,, ,,	0.875
Hydrochloric	16.0 ,, N/2	200.0
Nitric	17.0 ,, ,,	212.5
Formic	5.5 ,, 2N	275.0

Very recently Weitz and Stamm (*Ber.*, 1928, 61, 1144) obtained the following comparative results with ferric hydroxide solution and different sodium salts:—

Sodium salt.	Chloride	Nitrate	Acetate	Fluoride	Iodate	Sulphate
Precipitation value.	1050	276	100	30	6.7	1

The foregoing results show that the precipitation values of iodate ion from iodic acid or iodates of sodium and potassium are of the same order as those of bivalent ions. Hence from experiments on coagulation we can conclude that iodic acid and iodates exist in aqueous solution at least partly as $H_2I_2O_6$ and $M_2I_2O_6$ and give out bivalent I_2O_6'' ions.

Hydrofluoric Acid and Fluorides.

It is well known that the determination of the vapour density of hydrofluoric acid at the ordinary temperature shows that there is molecular association in the gaseous condition. Moreover, the boiling point of liquid hydrofluoric acid is much higher than those of liquid HCl, HBr and HI and this proves that hydrofluoric acid in the liquid condition is associated.

Jäger (*Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1901, 27, 28) from the reaction between hydrofluoric acid and mercuric oxide, and Abegg *ibid.*, 1903, 35, 137) from the reaction between hydrofluoric and boric acids concluded that hydrofluoric acid in aqueous solution consists mainly of H_2F_2 .

Pellini and Pegoraro (*Zeit. Elektrochem.*, 1907, **13**, 621) conclude that the conductivity of the acid with successive additions of alkalis shows a maximum when alkali equivalent to half a mole of hydrofluoric acid has been added and there is an abrupt change in the slope of the conductivity curve when an equivalent of alkali has been added. This behaviour is characteristic of typical dibasic acids and hence it might be assumed that hydrofluoric acid is dibasic.

Kremann and Decolle (*Monatsh.*, 1907, **28**, 917) have concluded from electric conductivity measurements of sodium fluoride that the acid is dibasic, although the measurements of Kohirausch and co-workers (*Das Leitvermogen*, 1916, 146) with fluorides of sodium and potassium do not agree with the results of Kremann and Decolle. Deussen (*Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1905, **44**, 300, 408) has assumed that hydrofluoric acid consists of a mixture of HF and H_2F_2 molecules. Hans Pick (W. Nernst's "Festschrift" 1912, p. 360) has assumed that HF molecules unite with F^- ions forming a complex HF_2^- .

The view that hydrofluoric acid and fluorides are associated in aqueous solution has recently been supported from coagulation experiments on different colloids with potassium fluoride. Ghosh and Dhar (*Kolloid Zeit.*, 1928, **44**, 149; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **5**, 303) showed that the precipitation values of potassium fluoride on sols of ferric hydroxide, ceric hydroxide, zirconium hydroxide, thorium hydroxide, chromium hydroxide and aluminium hydroxide are of the same order as those of potassium sulphate or oxalate. Similar result has very recently been obtained by Weitz and Stamm (*loc. cit.*) with ferric hydroxide sol and sodium fluoride.

Hence it appears that hydrofluoric acid and fluorides exist in aqueous solution at least partly as H_2F_2 and M_2F_2 .

Chromic Acid and Chromates.

In a previous paper (*Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1922, **121**, 99) I have advanced the view that chromic acid exists in solution mainly as H_2CrO_4 . The first dissociation constant of this acid is exceedingly high and the second dissociation constant is very small. I have now determined the second dissociation constant of chromic acid from the increase in the solubility of carbonic acid gas in solutions of potassium chromate (compare Datta and Dhar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, **107**, 824). The following results were obtained at 30°.

Original concentration of K_2CrO_4 .	Original concentration of $CrO_4^{=}$ ions.	Concentration of $HCrO_4^-$ ions.	Final concentration of $CrO_4^{=}$ ions.	Concentration of H^+ ions.	Second dissociation constant of chromic acid.
1.000 N	0.5837	0.3124	0.2713	$\frac{3 \times 10^{-7} \times .056}{0.3124}$	4.66×10^{-8}
0.500 N	0.3175	0.2016	0.1159	$\frac{3 \times 10^{-7} \times .056}{0.2016}$	4.79×10^{-8}

Hence, it will be seen that the second dissociation constant $\left(\frac{H^+ \times CrO_4^{=}}{HCrO_4^-}\right)$ of chromic acid is exceedingly small and that this is why all normal chromates are alkaline towards indicators.

Sherrill (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 29, 1641) determined the second dissociation constant of chromic acid and by conductivity and partition coefficient methods and obtained the value 7.4×10^{-7} at 25°.

Koppel and Blumenthal (*Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1907, 53, 228) determined the boiling points of aqueous solutions containing increasing amounts of CrO_3 . In the following table, I have calculated the values of i from the measurements of Koppel and Blumenthal.

CrO_3 in 100 g. of water.	Observed b. p.	' i ' calc. as H_2CrO_4 .	' i ' calc. as $H_2Cr_2O_7$.
12.12	102°	2.95	5.90
31.72	104°	2.25	4.50
57.40	107°	2.17	4.34
82.36	110.5°	2.17	4.34
120.05	116°	2.38	4.76
159.92	120°	2.23	4.46
247.7	127°	1.95	3.9

The foregoing results show that when CrO_3 is dissolved in water, the resulting solution exists mainly as H_2CrO_4 and H^+ and $HCrO_4^-$ and $CrO_4^{=}$ ions and not as $H_2Cr_2O_7$ and H^+ and $Cr_2O_7^{=}$ ions. Similarly the measurements of the freezing points of solutions of chromic acid by Sherrill (*loc. cit.*), Kremann (*Wien. Akad. Ber.*, 1911, 120, iib, 339), Büchner and Prins (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1913, 81, 113) and Cornec (*Ann. Chim. Phys.*, 1913, (8) 29, 491; 30,

63) are more in support of the view that chromic acid is mainly H_2CrO_4 and not $\text{H}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$. It is quite possible that in concentrated solutions and in presence of acids, we may get some $\text{H}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ molecules and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ ions, but in dilute solutions and in presence of alkali H_2CrO_4 and CrO_4^{2-} ions are stable. Recently we have shown that sols of silicic, vanadic, molybdic and tungstic acids become less polymerised in presence of small quantities of alkalis, and in presence of acids the polymerisation is increased.

Moreover, from Walden's measurements (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1888, 2, 49) it will be seen that the difference between the equivalent conductivities of a solution of potassium dichromate at a dilution of 1024 and $32=10\cdot2$, whilst the value is $20\cdot8$ for potassium chromate. This shows that potassium dichromate in aqueous solution exists mainly as KHCrO_4 .

Not much light regarding the constitution of chromic acid and chromates is thrown by the experiments on coagulation of ferric hydroxide sol by chromic acid and its salts. With aluminium hydroxide sol however, some interesting results have been obtained by Weiser and Middleton (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1920, 24, 680) and they are as follows.

Precipitation Values of Potassium Salts.

			Amount required.	Precipitation values in milliequivalents.
Ferricyanide	1.50 c.c. N/100	0.400
Citrate	1.70 ,,	0.438
Sulphate	2.10 ,,	0.538
Oxalate	2.75 ,,	0.700
Chromate	5.15 ,,	1.300
Dithionate	6.4 ,,	1.625
Dichromate	7.0 ,,	1.775
Chloride	11.0 c.c. N/2	14.7

According to the view advanced in a previous paper a solution of potassium dichromate is likely to be partly decomposed in water according to the following equation:—

Hence the precipitation value of dichromate should be greater than that of chromate, because from a dichromate solution the amount of CrO_4'' is less than that available from a solution of chromate of equivalent concentration. Recently Weitz and Stamm (*loc. cit.*) have obtained the following results on the coagulation of ferric hydroxide sol:—

Salt.	NaCl	Na_2SO_4	$\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$	NaH_2PO_4	Na_2HPO_4
Precipitation value.	920	1	1	0.7	0.5

It will be evident that the precipitation value of sodium dihydrogen phosphate is appreciably greater than that of disodium hydrogen phosphate, because more divalent and trivalent negative ions are available from the latter salt than the former.

It is well known that a solution of disodium hydrogen phosphate is alkaline towards phenolphthalein and a solution of sodium dihydrogen phosphate is practically neutral. The precipitation values of both these phosphates are appreciably smaller than those of the divalent negative ions. It appears therefore that the few trivalent phosphate ions which are available from the (above) phosphate solutions exert their influence on the coagulation of ferric hydroxide and thus the precipitation values of both disodium hydrogen phosphate and sodium dihydrogen phosphate are smaller than those of the bivalent anions. Moreover, from the foregoing considerations it will be clear that though the precipitation value of potassium chromate on aluminium hydroxide sol is smaller than that of potassium dichromate, the two precipitation values should not differ highly, because the few CrO_4'' which will be given out from HCrO_4' will exert their influence on the coagulation of the sol.

Summary.

1. Measurements of electric conductivity, lowering of freezing point and elevation of boiling point of solutions of iodic acid show that it is partly polymerised. Experiments on coagulation with ferric hydroxide sol and iodates and iodic acid show that iodate ions exist in the bivalent conditions as $\text{I}_2\text{O}_6''$. Similarly the view that

hydrofluoric acid and fluorides are associated in aqueous solution is supported from coagulation experiments on different sols. The precipitation values of potassium fluoride and potassium iodate on positively charged sols is of the same order as those of potassium sulphate and oxalate.

2. The second dissociation constant of chromic acid is very small and is of the order 5×10^{-8} . Electric conductivity and coagulation experiments are in favour of the view that potassium dichromate in solution exists partly as KHCrO_4 .

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY OF ALLAHABAD.

Received August 18, 1928.